

D6.4 INTEROPERABLE DIGITAL TWIN BUSINESS AND DECISION- MAKING PROCESSES

Philip Nathorst-Westfelt, Dan Engström, Ellen Göransson, Maja
Johansson Leather (Plan B), Irina Stipanovic (INFCON), Rahul
Tomar (DTT)

@AshvinH2020

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Task leader/Main author	Philip Nathorst-Westfelt (Plan B)
Contributing partners	Dan Engström, Ellen Göransson, Maja Johansson Leather (Plan B), Irina Stipanovic (INFCON), Rahul Tomar (DTT)
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ABSTRACT

This deliverable summarises the results of Task 6.4 *Lean life-cycle process mapping*. The purpose of this document is to present formalised process maps for the ASHVIN-developed tools of 4DV-C, DES, CMT, and SMT, all concerning the construction phase of construction projects; specific focus was put on decision-making routines concerning productivity, resource efficiency, and safety. The work was conducted in close collaboration with work conducted in WP4 concerning the four tools and their application at demonstration sites, as well as WP1 with its interoperability and ontology framework. The business process decision-making process models were developed with interoperability to the ASHVIN platform and interconnectivity in mind. Further, the integration of Lean Construction methodology was integrated into the process models. The process model mapping languages of BPMN and IDEF0 were used to map out the processes to provide standardised notation language, enabling the adaption of the ASHVIN tool process within multiple markets.

KEYWORDS

Digital Twin, Building Information Modelling, Lean Life-Cycle, Process Mapping, Interoperable, Decision-Making, Productivity, Resource Efficiency, Safety, Cost

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

4D	Four-Dimensional
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BPM	Business Process Management
BPMN	Business Process Modelling Notation
CMT	Configuration Management Tool
ConDT	Construction Phase Digital Twin
DES	Discrete Event Simulation
DEVS	Discrete Event System Specification
DT	Digital Twin
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
IDEF0	Integration Definition for Function Modelling
IDM	Information Delivery Manuals
IoT	Internet of Things
JIT	Just In Time
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LC	Lean Construction
LM	Lean Management
LOIN	Level of Information Need
LPS	Last Planner System®
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
PDF	Partial Differential Function
PDF	Probability Density Function
PDSA	Plan-Do-Study-Act
PI	Performance Indicator
PIM	Project Information Model
QC/QA	Quality Control / Quality Assurance
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TPS	Toyota Production System
TRL6	Technology Readiness Level 6

WP	Work Package
WPP	Work Process Pattern

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims to enable the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European-wide digital twin standard, an open-source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collection of real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT-based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimisation of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behaviour of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence-based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualisation methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security/privacy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is part of Work Package (WP) 6 of the ASHVIN project titled “*Social Innovation, and Standardisation*”. The WP has the aim of developing standardised implementation of digital twins (DTs), in the form of, privacy, safety, productivity, processes and decision-making. This delivery addresses the outline for T6.4 Lean life-cycle process mapping.

In previous work conducted in the ASHVIN project, several tools designed to meet a specific purpose of the ASHVIN platform have been developed. These tools have been separated into three stages of the construction process, planning, construction, and maintenance. This deliverable and its underlying task will be looking at the four tools developed specifically for the construction phase of this process. These four tools are the following: Construction Sequencing (4DV-C) developed in T4.6, Configuration Management Tool (CMT) developed in T4.5, Discrete Event Simulation (DES) developed in T4.2, and Safety Management Tool (SMT).

To reach the aim of the deliverable, of developing standardised formalised processes, the BPMN and IDEF0 specifications will be utilised for the processes will be using a formal and standardised “language” meaning it can be implemented in multiple markets. To this end, these four tools will be analysed in terms of their application to three demonstration sites for which the ASHVIN project has utilised to test the tools within the decision-making processes will be the focus of the formalised processes developed, as decision-making is one of the main advantages that the DT concept enables, with better real-time and accurate information, decisions can be made on objective data (Bakht and El-Diraby, 2015).

1.1 Background

Construction projects are inherently complex and dynamic, encompassing multiple stakeholders involved in multi-year endeavours (Qazi *et al.*, 2016). The multiplicity of stakeholders inherently leads to diverse sources of information. This information, increasingly in the form of data, is steering the construction industry towards a data-driven future. DTs have the aim of congregating project data connected to one platform. Decision-making processes within this evolving landscape are progressively reliant on objective information, which is grounded not only in historical successes but also in comprehensive simulations (Popkova *et al.*, 2019). This shift underscores the critical role of data in shaping the future of construction project management and decision-making. With the adoption of the DT concept for the construction industry, the capabilities of increasing the data-driven aspect of the industry are enabled even further, through the automatization of decision-making processes (Popkova *et al.*, 2019). The DT concept of which the ASHVIN project operates offers wide opportunities to involve and integrate IoT and AI to a greater extent than what has been possible for the construction industry in its conventional and historical context (Boje *et al.*, 2020).

In the context of the ASHVIN initiative, “*D1.4 Digital Twin Interoperability in the Construction Industry*” emphasised the development of four pivotal tools designed to enhance project managers' capabilities in improving productivity, resource efficiency,

and safety during the construction phase (Hartmann, Kennedy and Ungureanu, 2022). The primary focus of D1.4 was on technological interoperability, facilitated through API integration as well as standardised data formats. Furthermore, “D1.2 An Ontology for Digital Twin Models for the Construction Industry” was also a helpful resource for this deliverable to give ontological context to the ASHVIN tools. Specifically, the chapter “ConDT: An ontology for the digital twin of an infrastructure during the construction phase” for which the ASHVIN tools of the construction phase are implemented (Khan, 2022). In contrast, this deliverable shift focusses on the process mapping of these tools, their lean life-cycle incorporation, and delving into the interoperability requirements associated with the processes.

This deliverable aims to delineate and explicate the business and decision-making processes supported by DTs. It proposes to systematically map out these processes employing standardised and formalised process descriptions, anchored in the principles of lean life-cycle methodology. Situated within the construction industry, this deliverable concentrates on the integration of DTs with lean lifecycle process mapping methods, highlighting potential enhancements in productivity, cost, resource-efficient, and safety. The growing prevalence of DTs in the construction sector enables varied applications, examined through the prism of lean lifecycle process mapping techniques concerning DTs. The overarching goal of this deliverable is to improve the standardisation aspect within the field of DT application and study, in alignment with the objectives pursued in the ASHVIN project. This endeavour aims to contribute to the broader discourse on digital transformation in the construction industry, advocating for the strategic incorporation of DTs and lean methodologies to drive advancements in construction management practices.

1.2 Objective and Intended Audience

The objective of this deliverable is to generate process models which can operate using the ASHVIN platform. The process models generated will enable project managers to successfully utilise the ASHVIN platform during the construction phase. In this deliverable, we apply several formal process mapping methods to document and formalise process models. The intended audience of this deliverable comprises consortium partners affiliated with the ASHVIN project, as well as the broader public of construction management personnel representing the principal contractor, specifically site managers and engineers, in addition to subcontractors and investors, particularly technical supervisors. The applicability of standards is contingent upon the nature of the process and the degree of formalisation it embodies. Within this report, several formal process mapping methods are employed to document and formalise process models for the developed ASHVIN tools. The primary objective of this deliverable is to articulate these processes to present a lean life-cycle methodology that is conducive to the outline. The outcome and delivery of T6.4 will be a formal process description, based on input from the demonstration projects of ASHVIN and their application use of DT data over time with a specific focus on decision-making routines concerning productivity, resource efficiency, and safety.

The construction sector presents opportunities for enhancement in productivity, cost efficiency, and safety. As the adoption of DTs becomes increasingly prevalent in the construction industry, their diverse applications become more apparent. This deliverable is conducted through the lens of lean lifecycle process mapping techniques within the context of DTs. The objective of this project is to contribute valuable insights to the evolving field of study and application, aligning and building upon the efforts undertaken in the ASHVIN project.

1.3 Existing Solutions

As for decision-making processes, the construction industry at large still relies heavily on human-centric decision-making, as data-driven processes and procedures are still in limited use throughout the industry. The conventional approaches within the industry today are not optimal and can lead to less-than-ideal outcomes, concerning safety for example (Khoshnava *et al.*, 2020). The expertise within the industry certainly leads to successful projects using the conventional method of human-centric decision-making, however, the amount of data that will be available to us simply outpaces our abilities to take all data-points into account when making decisions (Boje *et al.* 2020). Here the opportunity to take advantage of technology comes into play.

The advent of Building Information Modelling (BIM) has brought some improvements in decision-making; however, the concept is mainly utilised by larger actors in the industry (Hong *et al.*, 2020). Certain software exist today which can help managers in making decisions and streamlining their procedures as best they can, however, these software/systems are often in the form of traditional scheduling tools that try to map out the construction activities along a timeline, such as a Gantt chart for example.

1.4 Outline

This deliverable is structured in the following manner. Introductory section to provide the reader with contextual information and background of the ASHVIN project and aim. The literature review chapter covers the theoretical areas of Business Process Mapping and Lean Construction (LC), as well as the interoperability and ontology of the ASHVIN project. Followingly, a methodology chapter is presented, where the framework is presented, for how the process models in the following chapter are created step by step.

The main chapter of the deliverable covers the process mapping of the four ASHVIN tools covered. Here, contextual background information of the tools is presented, then the actual process map(s) for each tool is presented, followed by the process model compliance, lean lifecycle integration, process interoperability, and lastly the decision-making routines of the process.

1.5 Relations to ASHVIN

The relationship of this deliverable to other works of the ASHVIN project primarily pertains to its emphasis on the construction phase within the project's scope of research. Specifically, Work Package 4 (WP4), which is dedicated to the Control and

real-time simulation of construction, served as a pivotal source of insights for the development of ASHVIN tools applicable to the construction phase. T4.3, which focuses on process mapping and Lean Construction (LC), inspired and served as a conceptual foundation for this deliverable. Additionally, the deliverable incorporated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) from T4.1, which are instrumental in tool-related decision-making processes. Furthermore, T4.2, centred on the DES tool, alongside T4.6 of the CMT and 4DV-C tools. For contextual understanding of interoperability and ontology, deliverables D1.4 and D1.2 were examined, respectively. Moreover, this deliverable establishes connections with WP6 outputs, specifically D6.1, which addresses standardisation, and D6.3, which discusses the integration of safety management processes.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In the following chapter, literature relevant to the deliverable is presented and contextualised. The first section of the chapter presents business process theory, including the IDEF0 and BPMN diagram methods, process decision-making, and formalisation and compliance. Followingly, an overview of the origin and history of lean production and its adoption in the construction industry in Lean Construction (LC) is presented. Furthermore, the theoretical context of the importance of interoperability is given and contextualised through the Construction Phase Digital Twin (ConDT) ASHVIN ontology. Last, the four ASHVIN tools for which process models are presented as well as the construction phase KPIs of the ASHVIN project.

2.1 Business Process Mapping

Business Process Mapping is done in all industries to improve the use of workflows and to enhance informational understanding (Krogstie, 2012). Employing business process models can aid in sense-making, understanding, communication, collaboration and the improvement and enhancement of the underlying business processes (ibid). The business processes should use model notation to depict the vital steps taken within a process and leave the lower levels of logic to external services. (Kluza, K. and Nalepa, G.J. 2019).

2.1.1 Process Model Theory

As the complexity of construction projects escalates, it becomes crucial to ensure that the processes governing these projects are devised and formalised to facilitate effective implementation and collaboration, regardless of the market. While a novel tool or task may appear promising in theory, its practical application hinges on the seamless integration of theoretical concepts with practical execution, a function that process models are designed to fulfil. The optimal utilisation of a tool is contingent upon an articulated and delineated implementation process. Additionally, adopting process languages comprehensible to all stakeholders can mitigate bottlenecks associated with information or data silos, enabling a unified understanding of the requisite steps for project completion (Borrmann, 2018). The applicability of standards is inherently involved in the formalisation of the process. This task employs multiple formal process mapping techniques to document and formalise process models comprehensively.

2.1.2 Process Model Languages

Mapping out processes that are to be shared across different languages and markets can be a tough task in certain instances, as there can be uncertainties and details that are left to interpretation and can therefore be misinterpreted. To manage this, mapping out processes in a visual format is a good way to enable ease of implementation with a limited chance of misinterpretations (Farshidi, Kwantes and Jansen, 2023).

Within the construction industry, three principal Process Modelling languages are predominantly utilised: Integration Definition for Function Modelling (IDEF0), Extended Event-Driven Process Chains (EPC), and Business Process Modelling Notation (BPMN). For the scope of this deliverable, particular attention was given to two of these languages, specifically IDEF0 and BPMN, in the context of the ASHVIN project and its associated tools. While IDEF0 represents an earlier generation of process modelling not as extensively adopted today as BPMN, it remains a relevant option for this deliverable's objectives. IDEF0 is notably effective in delineating complex processes with a structured approach. Conversely, BPMN offers a methodology that is both accessible and flexible in its notation, facilitating ease of understanding and adaptation (Farshidi, Kwantes and Jansen, 2023).

2.1.2.1 Integration Definition for Function Modelling (IDEF0)

The Integration Definition for Function Modelling (IDEF) was initially developed in the late 1970s by the United States Air Force and has been widely adopted across various business sectors since then (Waissi et al., 2015). Within the IDEF family of models, IDEF0 stands out as particularly suited to meet the contemporary demands of process modelling, characterised by its ease of modification, standardisation, rule-based structure, flexibility, scalability, and capacity to support modular and adaptable methodologies (ibid). IDEF0 facilitates the creation of three-dimensional process maps, allowing for the inclusion of pertinent information to enhance the description of each step within a process. This is done through nodes, which are the activity functions of IDEF0, where a node can be broken down into a sub-process (Tanyer & Aouad, 2005). This methodology enables the articulation of complex processes, the identification of redundant steps, and the clear communication of the procedures outlined in the diagrams (ibid). The IDEF0 method is formalised under the ISO/IEC/IEEE 31320-1:2012 standard, which provides a set of syntax and semantics for standardised implementation (ISO, 2019).

Figure 1 below illustrates the general contextual methodology underlying the IDEF0 method. **Functions (Boxes):** The basic building blocks of IDEF0 are rectangle shapes, known as boxes or blocks, each representing a specific function or process within the system (Tanyer & Aouad, 2005). These functions are usually labelled with a verb-based phrase.

- **Arrows:** There are four types of arrows used to connect the boxes, representing the flow of data and control:
 - **Inputs:** These arrows enter the left side of a box and represent the data or material needed for the function to occur.
 - **Outputs:** These arrows exit the right side of a box, showing the data or material produced by the function.
 - **Controls:** Arrows entering the top of a box. They represent the controls or constraints that guide or affect the functioning.
 - **Mechanisms:** These arrows enter from the bottom of the box and denote the means, tools, or mechanisms used to perform the function.

Figure 1: Visualisation regarding the IDEF0 technique, (IDEF, 2024).

Moreover, the IDEF0 methodology employs a *hierarchical* structure, wherein the top-left diagram provides an overarching view of the system, and subsequent levels, descending towards the right. Each function box within the hierarchy is assigned a unique identifier, facilitating the tracking and further decomposition of functions that require more detail into sub-levels diagrams. To enhance clarity in complex diagrams, *annotations* and *legends* may be incorporated, offering textual explanations that explain the diagram's contents. The IDEF0 approach allows for the graphical representation of a system or subject, constructed purposefully from a specific perspective. Jongeling and Olofsson (2006) present an example of a process modelled using the IDEF0 diagram in Figure 2. This process map inspired the development of the 4DV-C tool process map, detailed in section 4.1. The process model from Jongeling and Olofsson (2006) covers the integration of scheduling of construction sequences into a 3D model, enabling the special and temporal dimensions into the model creating a 4D model which can be used to visualise and quantify work.

Figure 2: Information flow shown with IDEF0 technique, (Jongeling & Olofsson, 2006).

2.1.2.2 Business Process Modelling Notation (BPMN)

Through the implementation of the BPMN process, you can simplify and make a process diagram more readable and easier to use. Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) is a graphical notation language suited for this purpose. BPMN presents, akin to IDEF a standardised language in which to present models for business processes and workflows. Originally developed by Business Process Management Initiative (BPMI) in 2004 and maintained today by Object Management Group (OMG), the latest version BPMN 2.0 was released in 2010 and will be the version utilised in this deliverable for developed process models (*About the Business Process Model and Notation Specification Version 2.0*, 2023).

BPMN proposes process-oriented mapping specifically for the business process domain, to be readable and understandable by all stakeholders in any business domain. This includes business analysts that will create adjust and refine processes, the technical personnel that implements the processes as well as business managers who are responsible for ensuring the processes are monitored and managed on a day-to-day basis. BPMN standardised as ISO/IEC 19510:2013, is well situated for the construction industry's digital transformation. It offers a standardised, graphical method for documenting all steps in construction processes, enhancing clarity and efficiency in communication. By presenting processes that fit the DT domain using the BPMN methodology, the construction sector can improve process management and transparency, ensuring seamless operations and collaboration across projects. This standardisation supports both technical and business stakeholders, enabling the representation of complex construction processes intuitively, thus facilitating better project planning, execution, and management (International Organisation for Standardisation, 2013).

As stated previously, BPMN is utilised throughout the construction industry, with one of these organisations being the buildingSMART Alliance, which has been utilising BPMN in the field of BIM as per the recommendation of the ISO 29481-1:2017 standard (International Organisation for Standardisation, 2017). Presented in Figure 3 are the elements of BPMN recommended by ISO 29481-1 (buildingSMART, 2023).

Figure 3: 22 elements of BPMN recommended by ISO 29481-1 (buildingSMART, 2023).

- **Flow Objects**

Flow objects of the BPMN method act as the main graphical elements for defining a business process. Flow objects include *Events* defined as circles, *Activities* defined as rounded rectangles, and *Gateways* which are defined as the shape of diamonds (von Scheel *et al.*, 2014).

- **Connecting objects**

Connecting objects within the BPMN notation depict the flow of activities, divided into three types, *Sequence Flow* defined as a solid line with an arrowhead, *Message Flow* defined as dotted lines with an arrowhead, and finally *Associations* defined with solely a dotted line (von Scheel *et al.*, 2014).

- **Pools and swim lanes**

Swim lanes act as separators within BPMN that can represent different roles/responsibilities. Swim lanes come in two types for BPMN, being *pools* and *lanes*. *Pools* represent different organisations or participants, whilst *lanes* can act to divide a pool into sub-partitions (von Scheel *et al.*, 2014).

- **Artifacts**

Artefacts represent information that can be valuable to mention within a process, these can include information such as *Data Objects*, *Groups*, or *Annotations* (von Scheel *et al.*, 2014).

- **Event types**

Event types are the representations of differing flow events, such as *Start*, *Intermediate*, and *End events* (von Scheel *et al.*, 2014).

2.1.3 Decision-Making of Process Models

This deliverable concentrates on the decision-making process of the process models developed, highlighting the importance of stakeholder understanding regarding the timing, methods, and rationale behind decision-making. In the development of a process model, it is imperative to encompass all elements integral to the process, including tasks, responsibilities, stakeholders, tools, and information. These elements

should be clearly defined, visible, and legible, as previously mentioned. Employing a process modelling language that uses formal graphical notations can aid in representing various process components, facilitating a simplified depiction of the entire process from inception to completion using standardised language.

In the area of decision-making, three distinct components set the basis for research within the field, being that of decision makers, decision tools, and decision techniques (Bakht and El-Diraby, 2015). Decision makers are mainly the project managers in the context of this deliverable and the tools researched. The decision tools are largely represented by the domain in which the decisions are made. The decision techniques are in this deliverable presented in the form of the developed process maps (ibid).

Regarding the decision-making processes within construction projects, it is observed that the industry's current solutions do not fully exploit the potential of existing technologies. Although some methodologies outperform others, there remains a significant gap between decisions informed by real-time or historical data and those made through traditional, manual approaches (Fang et al., 2018). The latter often fails to encompass the comprehensive analysis of all pertinent variables and details necessary for informed decision-making within construction projects. Despite extensive experience, even the most seasoned professionals are unable to account for every factor, leading to suboptimal and inefficient decision-making outcomes. In essence, construction field decision-makers frequently base their judgments on incomplete data due to the absence of effective decision-support tools and techniques. The lack of involvement of data-driven approaches is also the result of these new technological advancements not having reached the same degree of integration as it has in other industries that have been able to increase efficiency, lower resource use, and increase safety factors (Fang et al., 2018).

Nonetheless, the transition towards data-driven decision-making marks a significant advancement for the industry. However, the insights and experiences of decision-makers, such as project managers, remain invaluable. The inclusion of a data-driven approach will facilitate better human decision-making (Fang et al., 2018). In this context, the decision-support functionalities of the ASHVIN platform, including its Key Performance Indicator (KPI) dashboards, become particularly relevant. These tools aim to enhance decision-making by integrating empirical data with professional expertise. Within process models, in particular, the decision-making aspect can be seen as certain points within the process model which incorporate some type of decision-making. These can either be driven by automatic procedures, where the process system can decide based on an empirical number basis, or through a manual intersection, where a professional will act and move the process forward through some sort of decision-making.

2.1.4 Business Processes Formalisation

The formalisation of processes in the construction sector is arguably more critical than in other sectors, owing to the unique characteristics and complexities inherent in the industry and its projects (Wood and Gidado, 2008). Construction projects typically involve a multitude of stakeholders, a trait common to many industries. However, the

construction sector is distinguished by the variability of stakeholder companies from one project to another and the complexity arising from this diversity. Additionally, construction projects are often shaped by the specific conditions of the construction site, as projects involve the physical element of construction, adding another layer of complexity and an aspect which is missing in more digital software-centric industries.

The significance of applying standards is particularly pronounced in the construction sector, where the nature and formalisation of processes can vary widely. In addressing this challenge, this task incorporates various formal process mapping techniques to document and formalise process models. According to Elgammal et al. (2016), a process is considered formally defined when it meets certain specified criteria or attributes. By ensuring that the business processes outlined in this deliverable adhere to stringent formalisation standards across two applied notation language methods, it is possible to establish standardised processes that are applicable in diverse markets. A key objective in the development of process mapping for this deliverable was to align with ISO standards, underscoring the emphasis on compliance with recognised international standards.

2.1.4.1 Process Model Compliance Framework

To ensure the integrity of the process models presented in this deliverable, a compliance framework for process modelling was initially established. This framework served as a guideline for the development of each process model. Table 1 delineates the process model compliance framework that every process model included in this deliverable is required to adhere to.

Table 1: Process Model Compliance Framework.

Compliance Areas	Process Model Compliance
Documentation	The process is documented in a clear and detailed manner. This documentation often includes written procedures, flowcharts, diagrams, or standard operating procedures (SOPs) that describe each step of the process. For the process models in this deliverable, all tasks/functions/events are written as imperative sentences, meaning that they issue commands/instructions for either the user or the software to perform an action that will progress the process.
Standardisation	Formalised processes aim to ensure consistency and uniformity in how tasks are carried out. Standardisation also helps reduce errors and variations in output from process utilisation. Applying process mapping methods that adhere to standards and the syntax and semantics of the method can help in standardisation.
Roles and Responsibilities	Individuals or teams involved in the process have defined roles and responsibilities. This clarifies who is responsible for what and helps prevent confusion or duplication of efforts.
Compliance	Some formalised processes may be designed to ensure compliance with legal or regulatory requirements, as well as standards. In such cases, adherence to the process is crucial for legal and ethical reasons. Utilising a graphical notation ensures that the logic of the process can be understood and utilised/replicated in all markets, this enables compliance checking as the process will utilise formal reasoning in its structure. Automation in checking for compliance that the business process follows the accepted notations used for the process model language in question, ensuring the rules are followed as they pertain to the standard of the language, this can be achieved for the BPMN Diagrams within this deliverable (Elgammal et al., 2016).
Ensuring process logic	Ensuring control-flow has been addressed as well as ensuring that all resources have been mapped out accurately for the process to function as intended, this can also include the timing of the process. For the process models in this deliverable, the authors considered standardisation as a tool to ensure that the process logic was followed when mapping out the ASHVIN tools.
Efficiency and Effectiveness	Formalised processes are typically designed to be efficient and effective, aiming to achieve the desired outcome with minimal wasted time, resources, or effort. Meaning the process should only include activities that contribute value to the process and to what the process aims to achieve (Madison, 2005).
Continuous Improvement	Organisations with formalised processes should have mechanisms in place to regularly review and improve these processes based on feedback, changing business needs, or technological advancements, being both smaller incremental improvements as well as larger changes (Madison, 2005). The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) framework can be used to this end El-Khalili (2019).

2.1.4.2 Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA)

The PDSA cycle represents a repetitive framework aimed at facilitating continuous improvement within the domain of process description. Given the variability of projects that may integrate the process maps from this deliverable, it is anticipated that some degree of incremental refinement or adjustment will be beneficial. Moreover, the process models delineated in this deliverable are predicated on the Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL6), indicating their experimental developmental stage, and implying that they have not attained full maturity for implementation. The incorporation of the PDSA cycle into the adoption of these process models may serve as a pivotal strategy to achieve satisfactory outcomes, as suggested by El-Khalili (2019). The phases of the PDSA cycle are delineated as follows:

Plan: Define the objectives and processes necessary to achieve results in line with the organisation's policies and requirements while identifying and mitigating risks and opportunities.

Do: Execute the process model as designed for the specific process.

Study: Observe and, where relevant, measure the performance of processes and their outcomes concerning the organisation's policies, objectives, and requirements, along with planned activities, and document the findings.

Act: Implement measures to enhance performance if needed. Such enhancements may be applied iteratively to continually refine processes.

2.2 Lean Construction

2.2.1 Lean Construction Principles

The conceptual framework of lean production finds its roots in the Toyota Production System (TPS), a lineage that became formally recognised in the academic and industrial realms in 1988 through the introduction of the term "*lean production system*". This terminology served as a universal label for TPS, marking the inaugural application of "lean" within the contemporary discourse. Subsequently, the notion of lean has undergone significant evolution, particularly within the context of industry 4.0, where it has been augmented by modern technological advancements (Gil-Vilda, Yagüe-Fabra, and Sunyer, 2021).

The integration of lean principles within the construction industry, as initiated by Koskela (1992), signifies a paradigmatic transition aimed at increasing efficiency, and enhancing productivity, safety, and quality of construction practices. This adaptation of lean manufacturing methodologies to address the distinct challenges of the construction sector is distinguished by a strategic focus on waste reduction, workflow optimisation, value maximisation, and cycle time reduction (Araújo, C. et al. 2022). Fundamental to this approach are strategies such as advanced planning and effective resource management. Traditional construction management techniques, including the Work Breakdown Structure, Critical Path Method, and Earned Value Analysis, are critiqued for their inability to facilitate a continuous production flow and for their

contribution to resource wastage (Ballard and Howell, 2004). LC endeavours to minimise inefficient processes while amplifying value-adding activities.

The concept of a process in lean methodology is defined by its constituent steps and the efficiency with which it transitions from one step to the next, aiming for a continuous flow with minimised resource waste (Freire and Alarcón, 2002). The effectiveness of the lean process methodology hinges on the elimination of unnecessary activity overlaps and the establishment of a seamless flow that engages every phase of the lifecycle, thereby optimising each process step without impeding others (ibid). Enhanced control and insight into resource allocation facilitate improved productivity and quality across all project dimensions, ensuring that all requirements are met before progressing to subsequent phases. Thus, a meticulously designed and efficient process flow that reduces waste can significantly enhance the quality of the final product (Gutierrez *et al.*, 2022).

Construction projects are inherently complex, often involving numerous stakeholders and disciplines working concurrently to maintain tight schedules (Yu *et al.*, 2009). However, this simultaneity can introduce delays and lead times, as certain tasks depend on the completion of others, leading to inefficiencies where resources cannot be fully optimised (Ogunbiyi, Goulding and Oladapo, 2014). By applying lean principles to map out construction processes, these challenges can be mitigated.

The lean life-cycle concept for the construction industry proposes a holistic approach of lean methodology, advocating for a comprehensive approach to construction projects that spans from initial planning through to construction, operation, and even demolition phases, with an eye towards repurposing materials from demolished assets. Whilst a single process will likely not be able to cover the whole life-cycle in this context, implementing processes that tie into the life-cycle aspect as a whole can still be achieved.

Despite the potential advantages of LC methods such as the Last Planner® System of Production Control (LPS), Value Stream Mapping (Yu *et al.*, 2009), and Just-In-Time (Bamana, Lehoux and Cloutier, 2019). This observation underscores the need for a shift in the industry's production philosophy towards a more profound comprehension and management of both conversion and flow processes. Such a shift aims to refine construction and project management practices, thereby reducing costs, abbreviating project durations, and enhancing quality control (Sepasgozar *et al.*, 2021). The DT concept can help in that regard, where a DT platform can host the single source of truth to which other systems and processes can connect (ibid).

2.2.1.1 Last Planner System

Initiated in 1992, the LPS represents a cornerstone in the domain of LC, known for its effectiveness in the planning and scheduling of construction project activities. This system is distinguished by its emphasis on collaborative engagement, ensuring that all stakeholders, particularly those responsible for executing the work, are actively involved in the process. LPS aims to reduce variability and enhance reliability in project scheduling, incorporating input from personnel engaged in the current phase of the project's life cycle (Heigermoser *et al.*, 2019). For instance, during the planning phase,

architects and design engineers are primarily involved, whereas the construction phase sees the participation of foremen and superintendents on-site engaging with the system.

As documented in D4.1, the Last Planner System's metric, Percentage Plan Complete (PPC), is identified as an asset in augmenting the productivity Key Performance Indicator (KPI) of the ASHVIN platform and its 4DV-C tool. This acknowledgement highlights the system's relevance and potential for integration in the development and refinement of the 4DV-C tool. Furthermore, D4.2, which focuses on the development of the DES tool, reiterates the LPS's significant promise for integration, indicating a strategic consideration for incorporating the system within the DES tool's framework. This integration aims at leveraging the LPS's strengths to enhance the planning, scheduling, and overall management of construction projects, thereby supporting the objectives of both the 4DV-C and DES tools. The structure of the LPS as shown in Figure 4, further integration of the LPS can be seen in D4.3.

Figure 4: Last Planner System (source: Leanconstructionblog.com).

2.2.2 Lean Methodology and Process Mapping

Business Process Management (BPM) is related to Lean Management (LM), however, there are certain differences between the two according to Uriona Maldonado et al., (2020). As stated by Uriona Maldonado et al., (2020) they both seek to improve the flow of processes and achieve a continuous flow, but whereas LM is human-intensive, focusing on improving the communication and delivery between people, BPM is instead technology-intensive, focusing on ensuring flow across a technology-intensive process. (Gonçalves, 2010; Uriona Maldonado et al., 2020) state that BPM is an approach for improving performance that combines information technology with process methodologies, covering a high level of business aspects such as business objectives, strategies, and value chains. In the real world, the domain of BPM and LM

will work in conjunction to be able to reach the optimal outcome, where both the technology-intensive focus as well as the human-intensive focus work hand in hand (Uriona Maldonado et al., 2020).

The primary aim of applying lean methodology within the construction sector is to enhance the process's overall efficiency, safety, and resource utilisation, thereby elevating productivity, ensuring safer work environments, and achieving greater operational efficiency (Heigermoser et al. 2019). Drawing upon the foundational insights presented by Koskela, (1992), the lean methodology's adaptation within the construction industry emphasises a shift towards process flow optimisation, moving away from traditional, activity-centric methods. This shift entails the transformation of the conventional sequential approach into a more integrated and continuous process flow.

Historically, the construction industry has favoured a sequential methodology due to the unique nature of construction projects, which was perceived as necessitating a tailored approach for each project. Nevertheless, the potential for applying a standardised lean methodology across diverse projects has been recognised, facilitated by the establishment of adaptable implementation strategies that accommodate the unique aspects of different construction endeavours.

Central to the lean methodology is the emphasis on value creation, which guides the prioritisation and optimisation of processes to align with core project objectives and stakeholder needs. The progression towards digitalisation within the construction industry has further propelled the adoption of lean methodologies. Despite the challenges posed by the current limitations of BIM technology, notably the scarcity of real-time data, efforts to integrate lean processes with digital tools are ongoing. It is through the implementation of LM-supporting processes that LC can see adoption within the industry (Nikakhtar, A. et al. 2015). An illustrative example of such integration efforts is the research conducted by Heigermoser et al. (2019), which explored the potential synergies between the LPS and BIM, proposing a framework for their integration to enhance project management and execution. Similarly, this deliverable outlines the integration of the LPS with the 4DV-C and DES tools, indicating a parallel approach to enhancing project management through the incorporation of lean principles within digital tools. The output of the LPS is the PPC when integrated with the 4DV-C tool, as identified in Deliverable D4.1.

2.3 Interoperability

Interoperability is an important aspect when developing tools for DT purposes. The required information and data that interacts with a construction DT will originate from various sources of different data-formats, as well as be operated with multiple stakeholders (Mallek, Daclin and Chapurlat, 2012). Of importance here is the integration of these data sources, ensuring that the DT platform can handle, process, and interact with the data as mentioned by da Rocha *et al.*, (2022) for the manufacturing DT domain. To achieve interoperability, adopting standards for data exchange, APIs and ontologies is essential. These enable the seamless exchange of information and ensure that DT systems can communicate effectively, both internally

and with external systems. The basis for enabling a functional foundation for interoperability of a construction DT is the basis of a BIM model (Nguyen and Adhikari, 2023). The focus on interoperability is not just about technology integration but also about enabling better decision-making.

The primary emphasis of this deliverable pertains to interoperability between tool implementation, a pivotal consideration within the scope of the ASHVIN project through mapping out processes in line with the concept of lean life-cycle. Interoperability denotes the fluid exchange of data and information among disparate systems, tools, and stakeholders engaged in a construction undertaking. Through the dissolution of data silos and the facilitation of proficient communication, interoperability augments collaborative efforts among stakeholders within a construction project. In the context of this deliverable and the broader ASHVIN project, the examination and delineation of the application of the innovation toolkit developed throughout the project's duration will constitute the focal point of the interoperability assessment.

Within the ASHVIN project, aiming to achieve the goal of interoperable DT business and decision-making processes, special attention was paid to the interoperability requirements among the utilised tools and data sources. This effort was conducted in close collaboration with T1.3, which sought to present the interoperability of data and information in the form of identifying Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) processes and Information Delivery Manuals (IDM) (Hartmann, Kennedy and Ungureanu, 2022). In Figure 5, an overview of the architecture of the ASHVIN platform is presented, where all the components enabling the ASHVIN platform to operate can be derived.

Figure 5: Overview of the Architecture of the ASHVIN platform

2.3.1 ASHVIN Platform Interoperability and Interaction

The decision-making points for the four ASHVIN tools are present processed and analysed information and data in a visual format, either in a dashboard of KPIs or through visualisations (special models, and temporal models). Below in Figure 6, the top layer of the ASHVIN platform from which the ASHVIN tools can be interacted is presented.

Figure 6: Top layer of the Ashvin digital twin platform for data analytics (Hartmann, Kennedy and Ungureanu, 2022).

An ASHVIN API was developed in T1.3, which enables the information and data to be accessed to and from the four associated construction ASHVIN tools as efficiently as possible, with a minimal amount of data exchange functions (Hartmann, Kennedy and Ungureanu, 2022). The reasoning behind this approach is to minimise the amount of data required to run the tools and provide value to the DT. The data processed within the system should only be data which is impactful and crucial for the ASHVIN platform and the associated tools to operate, as the amount of data within a DT system can otherwise cause issues regarding bandwidth. The developed ASHVIN API provides data models to manage the activities of the ASHVIN tools, including Partial Differential Functions (PDFs) for the DES tool productivity rates, KPIs, and associated requirements (ibid). The API was designed using the open data standard of the OpenAPI Specification (OAS) 3.1.0, enabling the use of the ASHVIN API outside of the ASHVIN platform.

Furthermore, the ASHVIN T1.3 proposed the implementation of a model and asset geometry server to provide the ASHVIN platform with the geometrical information which the ASHVIN DT project requires for visualisation purposes. For construction DT purposes, the building asset model itself does not suffice as the DT will also require geometrical information on the construction site itself, temporary construction objects, as well as construction equipment and workers.

2.3.2 Construction Phase DT Ontology Enabling Interoperability

To enable interoperability of the ASHVIN tools, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) should be implemented in the form of an ontology for what parameters and functionality are supported within each phase of a construction project. This approach

both ensures that the same ontology framework can be followed throughout a project life cycle and ensures that interoperability across and between systems and tools is enabled where classifications can be followed.

The ConDT ontology covering the construction phase of a project includes 5 elements (*DataResources*, *BuiltEnvironment*, *Processes*, *DigitalAsset*, and *Outcomes*) as presented in Figure 7 from D1.2 (Khan, 2022). Whilst this deliverable has its focus on the *Processes* element, the interoperability and connection to the other elements of the ConDT ontology will also be investigated.

Figure 7: ConDT ontology and its sub-classes (Khan, 2022).

2.3.2.1 DataResources

The *DataResources* classification stands for the input parameters and are the different data sources of which the processes of the ASHVIN platform enable it to operate. For the ASHVIN platform, this element covers the

2.3.2.2 BuiltEnvironment

The *BuiltEnvironment* classification stands for the classifications of the built environment of construction projects and the construction site itself. Through this classification framework, which follows the IEC/ISO 81346 standard as proposed by IEC 81346-1, (2009), construction elements (including temporary construction elements) are categorised with the three areas of *Function Aspects*, *Product Aspects*, and *Location Aspects* classified (Khan, 2022).

2.3.2.3 DigitalAsset

The *DigitalAsset* classification framework stands for the DT representation parameters of a construction DT, including what data and information it should be able to represent. For the ASHVIN platform, these are the following: *Digital Representation Parameters*, *Project Information Model (PIM)*, *Information Container*, *Database and File Management*, *Schedules and Sensor Data*, *Level of Information Need (LOIN)*, and *Sensor Integration* (Khan, 2022). The digital asset classification provides a framework for the creation, management, and use of construction DTs, focusing on the digital representation model, information sharing, and real-time data integration for accurate built environment analysis (Khan, 2022).

2.3.2.4 Processes

The *Processes* in the context of the deliverable are presented below in Table 2. The four ASHVIN tools researched from a process model perspective in this deliverable

are presented with a short description of their purpose. The four tools aim to cover different use cases during the construction phase of the construction project. These include the likes of *LeanPlanning*, *SiteMonitoring*, *ConstructionSimulation*, *VersionManagement*, *ConfigurationManagement*, *StateManagement*, and *RiskManagement* as described in D1.2 (Khan, 2022).

Table 2: ASHVIN tools of the construction phase (Łukaszewska, 2021).

ASHVIN Tool	Description
	<p><u>Construction monitoring tool with productivity and safety KPI decision-making dashboard</u> - A 4D tool visualising past construction activities based on activities tracked by the digital twin platform. The tool allows planning of future construction sequences and site layout options based on accurately mapped past activities. Utilises the <i>ConstructionSimulation</i>, <i>LeanPlanning</i>, and <i>RiskManagement</i> class.</p>
	<p><u>Simulation-based real-time construction site and logistics planning tool</u> - A tool to set-up discrete event-based stochastic simulations of planned construction activities and site layouts. The tool will use stochastic productivity data tracked with the ASHVIN platform. Uses the <i>LeanPlanning</i> class</p>
	<p><u>Privacy ensuring safety management, simulation, and training tool</u> - A tool that will allow safety managers to understand possible safety hazards on site and to analyse past construction activities without being able to target specific workers personally. Uses the <i>SiteMonitoring</i> and <i>RiskManagement</i> class.</p>
	<p><u>A configuration management tool to track as-designed and as-built, as well as, to allow for seamless commissioning</u> – A tool that will allow for establishing and maintaining consistency among requirements, design, configured items, and associated construction, operations and maintenance data, equipment, and other enablers throughout the project lifecycle based on digital twin data. Uses the <i>QualityControl</i> and <i>ConfigurationManagement</i> class.</p>

2.3.2.5 Outcomes (Key Performance Indicators)

The *Outcomes* generated for the construction DT are the KPIs for the ASHVIN project. These are the outcomes of the construction phase ASHVIN tools and stand as the *decision-making points* of the tools. The KPI dashboard of the four tools all provide different metrics based on input, analysis, and processing to enable the user to assess and evaluate the process outcomes of the tools. The KPIs identified are *productivity*, *resource efficiency*, *safety*, and *cost*. These constitute various performance indicators (PIs) which are quantifiable and measurable sub-criteria of a KPI. In Figure 8 below, the ASHVIN KPIs for the construction phase tools of this deliverable are presented, the “outcomes/benefits” for each of the four specific ASHVIN tools do not consist of all four KPIs or all PIs therein, however.

Figure 8: DT-related outcomes during the construction phase (Khan, 2022).

2.3.3 Construction DT Interoperability APIs

In Table 3 from D1.2 the Interoperability APIs concerning the four ASHVIN tools are presented (Khan, 2022). For the interoperability sections for each ASHVIN tool, the specific involved APIs will be presented.

Table 3: Construction DT Interoperability APIs (Khan, 2022).

API	Description
/activities	Returns a list of activities
/pastactivities	Returns a list of activities completed and running to the current date.
/environmentalconditions/{activityID}	Get the possible environmental conditions that might influence an activity
/pdf/{activityID}/{environmentalconditionID}	Get a probability density function (pdf) for an activity
/schedulescenarios	Returns the scheduled scenarios
/constructionElement	Returns a list of construction elements
/requirements/{constructionelementID}	Returns a list of requirements for a construction element
/componentstatus/{requirementID}	Gets the automatically calculated status of a construction element's requirement
/kpis	Gets all KPIs for the project
/safetykpis	Gets all Safety related KPIs for the project

3 METHODOLOGY

To create formalised processes, several steps need to be considered. Primarily, there must be an understanding and knowledge of the underlying tool/process to be mapped out. Throughout the development of the ASHVIN tools, several construction project demonstration sites were assigned to test the different areas of interest of the ASHVIN project, being that of design, construction, and maintenance. The different ASHVIN tools (11 in total) were then developed along the ASHVIN project to meet the set KPIs for the project.

3.1 Creation of Interoperable Process Models

3.1.1 Selection of Process Model Methodology

The initial phase of the process model mapping of this deliverable involved determining the appropriate process model methodology for mapping the four ASHVIN tools under consideration. The selection between IDEF0 or BPMN process diagram methodologies was contingent upon the specific application of the tool and its inherent characteristics. The decision was guided by the overarching structure of the process, which informed the adaptation strategy.

3.1.2 Generation of Process Models

The creation of process models was informed by a detailed tracking of the steps undertaken for the tool applications at the demonstration sites. This approach ensured that the process mapping accurately reflected the operational logic of the tools as implemented within this deliverable and the ASHVIN project. The demonstration sites where the ASHVIN tools were deployed provided essential guidance in this endeavour. Consequently, the process models were aligned with the procedures observed at these sites, encompassing all four tools developed under the ASHVIN initiative concerning the construction phase. All process maps within this deliverable were generated using the software Microsoft Visio.

3.1.3 Ensuring Process Model Compliance

To guarantee compliance across each modelled process, a comprehensive process model compliance framework was established and implemented. This framework encompassed a variety of attributes, including *Documentation*, *Standardisation*, *Roles and Responsibilities*, *Compliance*, *Assurance of Process Logic*, *Efficiency and Effectiveness*, and *Continuous Improvement*. Each attribute was evaluated to ensure adherence within every process model. The detailed compliance framework is documented in section 2.4.1. Furthermore, for each of the process models generated using the BPMN methodology, the validation function within the Microsoft Visio software was used to ensure process logic.

3.1.4 Analysis of Process Models and Lean Construction Integration

The development of process models also considered the integration of LC principles, reflecting a commitment to embedding a lean mindset within the mapping of the tools. Given that the KPIs for the tools encompassed productivity, resource efficiency, safety, and cost. The process models were developed to enable the processes to take these performance indicators into account, generally, this was done through the decision-making visualisation dashboard and the decision-making KPI dashboards which the ASHVIN platform enables. The advantage in a lean context concerning the ASHVIN tools is therefore inherently included within the tools.

3.1.5 Addressing ASHVIN Process Interoperability Needs

For process models that describe a process of a DT platform, the interoperability and integration across processes and platforms and adjacent systems is of importance. For each of the process models generated in this deliverable, the interoperability of the processes was explored, to this end, the deliverable provides insight into the data inputs and outputs of the processes. The main interactions in the domain of interoperability for the ASHVIN tools utilise the developed open ASHVIN API, based on OAS. The ontological ConDT framework of D1.2 was utilised to provide the ontological context for the interoperability and involved elements and framework classifications that enable the ASHVIN tools to operate and interact with the ASHVIN platform.

3.1.6 Process Model Decision-Making Points and Implementations

Last, the decision-making component of the process models was explored. This analysis covered both automatic decision-making points, triggered by data within the process, and points requiring human interaction. The implementation of ASHVIN tools at the respective demonstration sites served as practical examples to illustrate the decision-making mechanisms within the processes described in this deliverable. The human interaction component of the decision-making within the process models is mainly done through the interpretation of data in the form of KPI dashboards as well as the visual elements enabled by the 3D/4D models of the ASHVIN platform.

4 PROCESS MAPPING

In this chapter, the process maps for each ASHVIN tool are presented following the methodology explained in Chapter 3. For each tool, the inherent purpose is first explained, and then the developed process map is presented with supporting information. The steps taken within the process maps are explained to provide documentation of what the steps entail, this includes input, platforms and data needed to run the processes. The process maps are then analysed based on the formalisation compliance framework from section 2.4.1. Followingly, the lean life-cycle integration is mentioned, and the interoperability of the processes is explained. In this step, a specific focus is put on the interoperability of the data and its interaction with the DT. Last, the decision-making points within the process models are provided, here the demonstration sites and their ASHVIN tool implementation are used as guidance for what, why and how decisions are to be made within a process. The four tools and their process mapping are presented in the following order, 4DV-C, DES, CMT, and SMT. The DES tool is integrated into the process of the 4DV-C tool, enabling the integration of the LPS LC concept. Furthermore, the 4DV-C tool stands as the basis for the tools of CMT and SMT to extend their application.

The original Microsoft Visio process model files and high-resolution PDF files can be found in the deliverable repository folder.

4.1 4DV-C - Construction monitoring tool with productivity and safety KPI decision-making dashboard

The 4DV-C tool, developed under the T4.6 tool is a construction sequencing tool that helps managers visualise past construction activities to help schedule planned activities utilising different resource configurations and construction site layout options. It uses 3D models and construction schedules and can help enable the planning of future construction sequences and site layouts through simulations which are based on previous construction examples by creating 4D visualisations. The transition from the base 3D model which is the BIM model to 4D is the addition of information that is the added dimension of integrating time and space to the model (Fischer et al., 2003). The 4DV-C tool also integrates a KPI dashboard to make comparisons, these KPIs are looking at the following indicators, productivity, resource efficiency, cost, and safety. The set of KPIs which is used to configure the input received is crucial to that end, as it is only based on the KPIs on which you can base your decision-making (Hartmann, Kennedy and Ungureanu, 2022; Khan, Duffy and Jungmann, 2023).

The integration of 4D BIM scheduling, which builds upon the foundational 3D BIM models by incorporating both time and spatial dimensions (Fischer et al., 2003), offers significant advancements in construction planning processes. By embedding the temporal dimension within 3D BIM models, it becomes feasible to map the progression of construction activities across time, improving productivity through the domain of special and temporal planning. This integration facilitates a comprehensive analysis of construction sequences, thereby enhancing strategy formulation for the preparation and execution phases. Such methodologies are particularly advantageous for

evaluating different construction site planning scenarios, optimally scheduling activities that carry higher risks to minimise those risks, and proactively improving onsite safety during the planning stage. The 4D BIM component of the 4DV-C tool will also spatial scheduling, as part of this approach, allow for the meticulous allocation of resources, particularly crucial for high-risk tasks, and aids in conducting thorough risk assessments based on simulations of planned activities. Additionally, the application of sensor technology to gather real-time data enables the monitoring of structural stability, ensuring it remains within safe parameters as compared to the planned thresholds.

Furthermore, the chosen model can be evaluated continuously with its 4D BIM framework counterpart throughout the construction phase. This continual assessment allows for the identification of any variances, thus improving overall control over the construction process. A proactive evaluation of each construction phase, including the foresight of potential coordination risks among different onsite disciplines, is a pivotal element of this integrated methodology. In this context, the 4DV-C tool and its visualisation and sequencing play a crucial role in disseminating information about potential risks within the established construction plan to all relevant stakeholders (Sulankivi and Kiviniemi, 2010). Moreover, considering the dynamic nature of construction sites, the inclusion of safety measures in the planning stages not only pertains to permanent structures but also encompasses temporary constructions and equipment (ibid).

4.1.1 4DV-C Process Model

The process map of the 4DV-C tool was developed using the IDEF0 methodology. The reasoning behind the decision to utilise the IDEF0 Diagram methodology for mapping the 4DV-C tool was the inclusion of the LPS within the process, the structure of the LPS fits well within the IDEF0 Diagram configuration. For the 4DV-C IDEF0 process map, several different figures are presented, which gives further clarity to the process context.

The process map of the 4DV-C tool is sequenced in five distinct activities (**A1-A5**) with accompanying *Input*, *Control*, *Mechanism* and *Output*. The activities follow the sequential method of IDEF0 where the activities depict the flow of functions through a step-by-step manner. Further, the second function of the 4DV-C process **A2** model is decomposed and broken down into a sub-function consisting of four functions (**A21-A24**). For this process the actual roles of those involved in the process are not clear, however, the use case for the 4DV-C is more so meant to serve as an informational guide when making decisions by project teams. The model of the 4DV-C tool complies with the rules of the IDEF0 notation as set out by ISO/IEC/IEEE 31320-1:2012, and was configured in Microsoft Visio.

4.1.1.1 4DV-C Process Model: Context Diagram

The *Context Diagram* of the 4DV-C tool is shown in Figure 9, this diagram shows the external *Inputs*, *Outputs*, *Controls*, and *Mechanisms* of the 4DV-C tool. Within the process model itself, you will find further *Inputs*, *Outputs*, *Controls*, and *Mechanisms*,

although these are internal to the model, going from function node to function node and are therefore not represented in the *Context Diagram*.

Figure 9: IDEF0 Context Diagram annotating the external Inputs, Outputs, Controls, and Mechanisms of the 4DV-C tool.

4.1.1.2 4DV-C Process Model: Node Tree

Figure 10 presents the 4DV-C *Node Tree* for the 4DV-C process model, here the functions of the process model can be visualised. From the figure, one can gain insight into the structure of the process and see that the process model includes a decomposition for node **A2**. The **A2** node process is presented in Figure 10 and shows a detailed process of the *4D Last Planner Visualisation Sequencing*, which also incorporates the DES tool within the process flow.

Figure 10: IDEFO Node Tree of the 4DV-C tool, representing the Top-Level A0 Node and the Decomposed Function A2 Node.

4.1.1.3 4DV-C Process Model: Top-Level A0 Node

A0 4DV-C tool

The A0 Node of the 4DV-C tool presents the main Top-Level process model and is presented in Figure 11.

A1 - Prepare location-based 3D models

The first step of the 4DV-C tool is to prepare a 3D model of the construction asset to be built. Of importance here is to ensure that the model includes enough information to enable 4D integration, this could be model requirements, examples being the classification of *ProjectInformationModel* from D1.2 (Khan, 2022).

A2 - Perform 4D Last Planner visualisation sequencing

This function is performed to output a 4D model including visualisation and sequencing of planned construction works as per site layout limitations and available resources. The process model for node **A2** is decomposed to show the function in more detail in the following section 4.1.1.4.

A3 - Evaluate planned KPIs and activity sequencing (ASHVIN Dashboard)

Through the integration of the dimensions of the temporal and spatial model in the previous function **A2**, the **A3** function is where the planning *decision-making point* of the process model is made. The prepared 4D visualisation and sequencing of the construction activities can be evaluated for the specific input parameters of the **A2** function. Through adjusting the input parameters for **A2** the user of the 4DV-C tool can

in this step gain insight into different site layout and sequencing options which can improve the outcome of the 4DV-C tool. By running the **A2** function multiple times, the optimal sequencing for the planned activities can be gained. The output of node **A3** constitutes the sequencing planning component of the 4DV-C tool. Nodes **A4** and **A5** are where the construction monitoring is performed.

Within this function, a model is presented that adheres to the LOD 400 level, as defined by the *DigitalAsset* class in D1.2. The *DigitalAsset* class works as the *Control* of the **A3** node, as the *DigitalAsset* class defines the digital representation parameters of the DT at the stage of sequencing planning, including *ProjectInformationModel*, *InformationContainer*, *LOIN*, and *Sensor* (Khan, 2022).

A4 - Integrate real-time data and parameters

Function **A4** is performed to integrate real-time data which will be measured against the chosen planned visualisation sequencing from **A3**. Through integration of the actual performed activities and data from the construction site insight can be gained for performing analysis and evaluation of the performed activities in production in the final function of the process model, **A5**.

A5 - Evaluate performed KPIs and activity sequencing (ASHVIN Dashboard)

In the last function node of the process model, the performed activities can be evaluated in the ASHVIN KPI dashboard for project follow-up. Here PIs for *Productivity*, *Resource efficiency*, *safety*, and *cost* can be evaluated against the planned sequencing of **A2**. The **A5** function and the 4DV-C will also you will be able to extract and output suggestions for improvements to the simulated sequencing for future implementations.

As proposed in D1.2, the *BuiltEnvironment* class can be used at this stage to categorise parameters for the built assets. The functional aspects, product aspects, and location aspects can be categorised (Khan, 2022).

Figure 11: IDEF0 Top-Level A0 Node and main process diagram of the 4DV-C tool.

4.1.1.4 4DV-C Process Model: Decomposed A2 Node

The **A2** function is decomposed in Figure 12 and follows the LPS methodology as shown in Figure 5 of section 2.2.2. Here, the LPS is used to provide the 3D model with scheduling information and input to transform the 3D model with temporal and special information required to output a 4D model which delivers data at a LOD 3 level with integration of the DES tool to provide optimal resource allocation and site layout options. As described in D4.3, the process model supporting lean project planning, control and risk management can be used in conjunction with the 4DV-C process model, particularly the **A2** function node within. Further, the decomposed **A2** function originates from D4.1, with minor adjustments to complement the overall 4DV-C process.

A21 - Formalise Product Breakdown Structure (PBS)

In function **A21** of the process model, the 3D BIM model is used as input as well as the Construction Planner as mechanism.

A22 – Schedule Construction Activities

For the **A22** function, the 3D BIM model with implemented PBS is used to schedule the construction activities. For the **A22** function, the DES tool of the ASHVIN project can be incorporated to provide discrete event simulation to the process of 4DV-C, description of the DES tool is provided in section 4.3.

A23 - Plan Activity Workspace Using Planning

The lookahead schedule is used to plan out activities of specific disciplines.

A24 - Visualise Activity Workspace

Potential options for selection of sequencing of construction works. The output of the 4D visualisation sequencing can be visualised along a time axis with all the performed activities, as well as through a KPI dashboard in the **A3** node, in which PIs can be measured and compared. After running the 4D visualisation sequencing several times with different site layout options as well as adjustments in the resource availability/options and activity sequencing, the output can be evaluated visually and numerically in the ASHVIN dashboard. Here the spatial element is combined with the temporal element with an output of a 4D model.

Figure 12: IDEF0 Decomposed A2 Node of the 4D Last Planner visualisation sequencing of the 4DV-C tool.

4.1.2 4DV-C Process Model Compliance

The process model for the 4DV-C tool was constructed in Microsoft Visio and conforms to the standard for the IDEF0 notation of ISO/IEC/IEEE 31320-1:2012 (ISO, 2019). The 4DV-C compliance framework is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: 4DV-C Process Model Compliance Framework.

Compliance Areas	4DV-C Compliance
Documentation	The process is documented in a clear and detailed manner using the 4DV-C diagram method. Beyond the Top-Level Node process model itself, the accompanying Context Diagram, Node Tree, as well as a decomposed process of Node A2 is provided.
Standardisation	The process model was developed using only IDEF0 assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC/IEEE 31320-1:2012 for syntax and semantics.
Roles and Responsibilities	The specific roles involved in the process of 4DV-C are not detailed in this process model, however, the process would likely involve stakeholders such as Design Managers, Project Managers, Construction Managers, Site Managers as well as construction firms and owners.
Compliance	The process model was developed using only IDEF0 assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC/IEEE 31320-1:2012 for syntax and semantics. Validation procedures for IDEF0 diagrams are not available, however, great care was taken to ensure the process model conforms to that of the ISO standard.
Ensuring process logic	As for ensuring process logic for the 4DV-C tool, the sequential nature of the IDEF0 mapping approach helped in this regard. Each function within the process is clearly defined with each node following the flow of the process and the tool.
Efficiency and Effectiveness	The process model was developed and designed for efficient and effective application, aiming to achieve the desired outcome with minimal wasted time, resources, or effort.
Continuous Improvement	As the ASHVIN project aims to achieve TRL6 level of maturity, the process model of 4DV-C is open for improvements and the original Microsoft Visio file can be provided for further development.

4.1.3 4DV-C Lean Lifecycle Integration

From an LC perspective, the 4DV-C tool can help the project manager evaluate options that meet the desired KPIs for planned activities. In general, resource utilisation can be optimised by running the 4DV-C tool as well as finding the sequencing that utilises the least resources and is optimised for productivity, resource efficiency, cost, and safety. Furthermore, through visualising the activities performed using the 4D temporal aspect, resources can be mapped out to provide the most effective sequencing, minimising wasted resources. With the knowledge of when resources such as personnel, equipment, and machinery will be used for any given activity, their utilisation will also be known proactively enabling tighter timelines and resource utilisation. Further, the 4DV-C tool can then subsequently be used to track real-time data and ensure that the schedule is followed. The 4DV-C tool integrates the DES tool and the LPS methodology in this regard, providing the user with the PPC of their performed activities.

4.1.4 4DV-C Interoperability

As for the interoperability regarding the 4DV-C tool, the ontology of *DataResources*, *BuiltEnvironment*, *DigitalAsset* classifications, and *Outcomes* comes into play and has been integrated into the process model in the form of IDEF0 *Controls*. Each of the 4DV-C IDEF0 nodes has the ConDT classifications as process model *Controls*, meaning that the interoperability and integration of *Inputs* and *Outputs* as well as the *Mechanisms* of the ASHVIN Platform conform to the ConDT classification rules and requirements.

As for interoperability of the 4DV-C tool and its application outside of the ASHVIN platform, there is a need for the visualisation on a 4D domain, as well as a method for presenting data in a format viable for decision-making, such as the KPI dashboard of ASHVIN. The 4DV-C tool integrates the DES tool in its scheduling.

For the 4DV-C tool, all developed and listed KPIs from Table 3 from section 2.3.2 are involved.

4.1.5 4DV-C Process Model Decision-Making Points and Implementations

To provide context of how the 4DV-C tool can be implemented in terms of decision-making routines concerning productivity, resource efficiency, and safety, demonstration site #10 of the ASHVIN project was chosen. Including a PPC example from demonstration site #6.

The main point of decision-making of the 4DV-C tool takes place in Node **A3** and **A5** where the user evaluates the planned and subsequently performed KPIs and activity sequencing through the ASHVIN KPI Dashboard and Visualisation Dashboard.

4.1.5.1 4DV-C Productivity KPI

The PPC of the activities are mapped out in sequence of construction works, this gives information on the Percent Plan Complete (PPC) of planned activities which can be compared to actual performed activities. Here the planned time can be compared to the actual time. The PPC is part of the LPS. The PPC will give the user a percentage score from 0% to 100%, generally, a good score is considered as 80-90% for performed activities compared to that of planned activities when measuring the planned construction works for a specific activity. Scores below 80% would indicate deviations outside the planned schedule of the weekly work planning and require an assessment of the performance regarding productivity, where the 4DV-C tool could indicate that something might be wrong. The actual performed activities can be compared using a Weekly Work Plan (WWP) to that of PPC.

Decision-making about productivity for the 4DV-C tool can be made with an assessment of the PPC score of the tasks, and if the score falls below a set target percentage, with a general recommendation of > 80%.

The PPC decision-making dashboard of demonstration site #6, is shown in Figure 13. Here the user can derive the *Completed*, *Delayed*, and *Stopped Tasks*.

Figure 13: 4DV-C Percentage Plan Complete Decision-Making Dashboard (Node 5).

4.1.5.2 4DV-C Resource Efficiency KPI

Smart quay walls of the Port of Rotterdam were the focus of demonstration site #10. Here the ability to increase the utilisation of the infrastructure is key to keeping the Port competitive was a goal of the project. The focus was the development of a finite element model as a predictive twin of the quay wall. The combination of monitoring data and finite element analyses will provide insight into physical mechanisms that enable an understanding of how the actual quay wall responds. For the Quay Wall demonstration site resource efficiency was measured for three indicators:

- Cumulative grout volume [m³]
- Grout flow [L/min]
- Number of lost casings during vibrio pile installation

An example of resource waste that could be calculated from the demonstration site was the lost casings over weekly periods.

4.1.5.3 4DV-C Cost KPI

The cost for each activity is given, here the calculation can include cost for both equipment and workers, both as resource input given. Depending on the sequencing and the productivity rate, the cost will be calculated and can be assessed to that of the planned vs performed.

For demonstration site #10, a breakdown is split into Construction Cost Breakdown (per m of quay wall) and that of % of Total Cost (per m of quay wall).

4.1.5.4 4DV-C Safety KPI

As for safety considerations when running the 4DV-C tool, structural stability was considered for the Quay wall. Here the planned maximum allowed displacement could be compared to the actual value during construction, tracked using sensor technology and measured in depth [mNAP]. Visualised in the 4DV-C KPI dashboard a Diaphragm

Wall Displacement graph can be seen in Figure 14. As can be seen in the graph the measured displacement was within safe parameters. The 4DV-C tool uses the *RiskManagement* classification to provide the safety factors within the KPI dashboard.

Figure 14: 4DV-C decision-making KPI Dashboard for performed activities (Node 5).

4.2 DES - Simulation-based real-time construction site and logistics planning tool

The DES tool, developed under T4.2 is designed to enhance construction planning by using real-time data-driven event simulation. The main objectives of the tool include improving productivity, ensuring resource efficiency, and enhancing safety in construction projects. The discrete event aspect of the tool is of focus here, as it is only when events occur that the DES tool that the system state changes, the duration of activities and their resource utilisation can be analysed and assessed, meaning that the tool does not consider in the form of simulation what occurs in between distinct events. By applying Discrete Event System Specification (DEVS) formalisms, the tool models construction site activities and evaluates their impacts. It integrates real-time data from DTs, allowing for dynamic management of construction sites. This innovative approach supports proactive decision-making and efficient resource allocation, addressing the complexity and unpredictability of construction environments. The DES tool models and simulates processes, with a focus on delivering KPIs on duration and resource usage (Jungmann, 2022). The DES tool can work in conjunction with the CMT tool developed in T4.6 to integrate visualisation within the ASHVIN platform.

The general information flow for the DES tool and its connection with the ASHVIN platform is visualised in Figure 15 (T1.3), which this deliverable builds upon by incorporating the LPS methodology introducing the decision-making flow of the process of DES, which was outlined in D4.2. This can be seen in the 4DV-C decomposed process model of the **A2** Node, as seen in section 4.1.1.4.

Figure 15: Information flow of the DES tool (Hartmann, Kennedy and Ungureanu, 2022).

4.2.1 DES Process Model

The DES tool is somewhat difficult to generalise in terms of process mapping, as the DEVS sub-model portion of the DES tool in which you specify and configure Work Process Patterns (WPP) for specific use cases can be somewhat different depending on what type of work is to be conducted. Here, the BPMN diagram was utilised where the process is described in Figure 16 and Figure 17, the process diagram also includes a general process layout of the DEVS sub-model using the sub-process feature of BPMN. The BPMN notation was suitable for the DES tool as it includes multiple functions as well as its useful sub-process functionality.

As for decision-making within the DES tool, the general applicability is the measurement of activity duration, and required resources. The DEVS sub-model looks at whether resources are seized or not, if so, the resources are put in a queue leading to wasted resources from a LC point of view. The DES simulation is finished, when no further activity is to be completed, with no more events to conduct. Based on this the output in terms of the KPIs can be measured and considered across multiple scenarios. The output which the DES tool will give you depends heavily on the input parameters, especially the activity duration, (Jungmann, 2022). Integral to the DES tool is the DEVS sub-model, which in turn gives output in terms of resources and whether these are seized or not. Furthermore, the DES tool integrates with the 4DV-C tool as can be seen in section 4.2, through this integration of LC through LPS.

Figure 16: Process diagram of the DES tool using the BPMN diagram method.

Figure 17: Sub-Process: Configure Work Process Pattern.

The implementation of formalisms within DES serves a critical role in aiding decision-makers to comprehend the functionalities and interactions of entities within construction process simulations. DEVS models for the DES tool need to be developed for new WPPs. These can be similar when it comes to certain types of work and different for others. Examples of WPPs developed in D4.2 for the ASHVIN project are Mounting prefabricated columns, Drywall installation, and Concrete works by crane. The process models for the work process patterns can be seen in Figure 18, Figure 19, and Figure 20.

4.2.1.1 DEVS Process Model: Mounting prefabricated columns

The DEVS process model for the mounting of prefabricated columns as seen mapped out in Figure 18 below follows the DEVS sub-model portion of the DES process model. The process enables a procedure for the mounting of prefabricated columns which can be simulated and planned in more detail using discrete event simulation. The process takes into account weather conditions and potential traffic for column delivery by trucks. Furthermore, the process is aimed at utilising the just-in-time (JIT) methodology by minimising storage requirements of materials at the construction site and instead

delivering continuously throughout the construction process as new materials are needed.

As for the inputs for the DES simulation of prefabricated columns, the number of columns required at the site, the number of columns per truck delivery, delivery intervals and mounting time can be simulated, adjusted, mapped out and evaluated. Additional potential parameters that can have an effect such as cost, and availability of resources are also used as input to measure and compare different options. The activity durations can also be adjusted through the modification of the Probability Density Functions.

Figure 18: DEVS Process Model: Mounting prefabricated columns.

4.2.1.2 DEVS Process Model: Drywall installation

In Figure 19 below, the DEVS process model for the finishing activity of drywall installation can be seen. Multiple different finishing activities and trades are conducted at construction sites that are similarly mapped in their process, such as ventilation, plumbing, electricity, painting, etc. For the ASHVIN project and the DES tool, only the drywall process was mapped out and showcased by a DEVS process model as an example of a Work Process Pattern (WPP) for finishing works. The general workflow for finishing activities is the check whether resources are available to conduct work both in the form of trade personnel and workspace availability. As each trade will only require a certain workspace size at once, multiple trades can conduct their work at the same time on a floor/construction area if the size of the construction site is large enough to accommodate. Each different trade will have different input resource parameters of duration, cost, number of workers etc. The finishing works simulation through the DES tool can enable the coordination of the multiple different trades that can then conduct their work simultaneously at a construction site, covering different trades at different locations of the site. The pull planning feature of the LC principles is incorporated into the DES of finishing works. The DES for finishing works can also be utilised to collect real-time data through data-driven PDFs of the work conducted at a

construction site. This can be used to track, detect, and minimise potential duration overlaps and area overlaps.

Figure 19: DEVS Process Model: Drywall installation.

4.2.1.3 DEVS Process Model: Concrete works by crane

In Figure 20 below, the DEVS process model for concrete works by crane is shown. Cranes are often a vital component for efficient construction sites, but they also mean the manipulation of heavy equipment and resources and must be respected in their operation as they carry risks. In line with this, careful and optimal planning of crane operations is of great importance, with concrete works through the use of cranes being one use case of cranes at construction sites. Construction sites of today can at times be quite limited in terms of space when work is conducted in urban areas, here the DES tool can be used to simulate and plan crane operation with the purpose of concrete works by crane. Concrete works are time-sensitive, with set times that must be met to ensure optimal concrete conditions and final quality and strength. With a WPP of the workflow required for the concrete works, for example, when the crane has poured out all the concrete of a concrete truck the next truck should be ready to quickly be able to switch out enabling a continuous flow of concrete where needed. Input parameters of the construction are needed for the DES tool for concrete works by crane, these are the number and costs of resources, including construction workers, cranes, crane operators, workspaces, and concrete truck parking location. Furthermore, the total concrete volume, concrete truck capacity, and delivery intervals are needed. As is the case with DES, the input parameters can be adjusted to offer different options which will enable a more optimal option to be available. The process will also require PDFs for each activity. As is shown in the process model, the DES

can also include the weather conditions at the site, where maximum allowed wind speeds can be given.

Figure 20: DEVS Process Model: Concrete works by crane.

4.2.2 DES Process Model Compliance

The process models for the DES tool were constructed in Microsoft Visio and have been validated to ensure the process models follow the standardised ISO standard for the BPMN notation. Below, in Table 5, the compliance framework of the DES process models.

Table 5: DES Process Model Compliance Framework.

Compliance Areas	DES Compliance
Documentation	The process models are documented in a clear and detailed manner using the BPMN diagram method.
Standardisation	The process models were developed using only BPMN assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC 19510:2013.
Roles and Responsibilities	The specific roles involved in the processes of DES are not detailed in the process models, however, the project manager would be involved in the use of the DES process.
Compliance	The process models were developed using only BPMN assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC 19510:2013. Further, the process models were verified and validated using the Microsoft Visio validation tool, to ensure the process models conform to the BPMN standard methodology.
Ensuring process logic	For the DES tool, process logic was taken into consideration when mapping out processes, following the logical steps taken within the tool. As the DES will be running in multiple interactions with adjustments to input parameters
Efficiency and Effectiveness	The process model was developed and designed for efficient and effective application, aiming to achieve the desired outcome with minimal wasted time, resources, or effort. The decoding process of the process reader should be a logical procedure (Winter et al., 2023).
Continuous Improvement	As the ASHVIN project aims to achieve the TRL6 level of maturity, the process models of DES are open for improvements and the original Microsoft Visio file can be provided for further development. For the DEVS formalism of the DES tool, depending on the specifics of the work process patterns, specific DEVS models will need to be produced.

4.2.3 DES Lean Lifecycle Integration

Whilst the DES tool in isolation might not necessarily integrate any lean methodologies in its process flow, the DES tool can be utilised in conjunction with the 4DV-C tool to aid with scheduling construction activities through discrete event simulation. It can however be stated that by running the DES tool many iterations to the point where the stochastic simulation process reaches stable predictions, you will be able to predict outcomes that provide the most efficient use of resources, planned for conducting activities in the most efficient way possible which will be presented in the ASHVIN KPI dashboard. This will lead to minimised resource waste and limited waiting times, both adding to the LC aspect. For the DES tool, the KPIs of productivity and resource efficiency present the lean integration through the LPS and its PPC which can be derived through the 4DV-C KPI dashboard.

4.2.4 DES Interoperability

The DES tool is complex, involving complex calculations and simulations to operate. When it comes to the data requirements for input and outputs, the DES tool follows the *DigitalAsset* Classification of ConDT through the *DES Database* inclusion. Through

the *DES Database*, the outputs and inputs of the DES tool can integrate with the DES process.

The DES tool also utilises the CMT tool for visualisation purposes, gathering data from the *CM Database* in that respect, this is done using JSON files. Furthermore, the output of the DES tool generates a scheduled scenario which is sent to the *ASHVIN DT Database*.

4.2.5 DES Process Model Decision-Making Points and Implementations

As for decision-making within the DES tool, the general applicability is the measurement of activity duration, and required resources. Integral to the DES tool is the DEVS sub-model, which in turn gives output in terms of resources and whether these are seized or not, if so, the resources are put in a queue leading to wasted resources from a LC point of view. The DES simulation is finished, when no further activity is to be completed, with no more events to conduct. Based on this the output in terms of the KPIs can be measured and considered across multiple scenarios. The output which the DES tool will give you depends heavily on the input parameters, especially the activity duration, (Jungmann, 2022). The main outputs derived from the DES tool are duration and resource usage, covering the areas of productivity and resource efficiency.

4.2.5.1 DES Productivity KPI

The productivity KPIs of the DES tool are presented below,

- Total Duration
- Productivity Rate
- Utilisation Rate of Equipment
- Number of Concurrent Trades

4.2.5.2 DES Resource Efficiency KPI

Through the DES tool operation, optimised resource efficiency parameters can be derived and presented in the DES KPI dashboard.

- Cost for Equipment and Workers
- Optimised Supply Chain
- Optimised Resource Allocation
- Optimised Site Layout

4.2.5.3 DES Cost KPI

The cost will be determined through the working time depending on the number of workers for the activity duration and the equipment necessary to conduct the planned work.

- Costs for Equipment and Workers

4.2.5.4 DES Safety KPI

The safety KPI of the DES tool can include the consideration of high-risk and hazardous activities. The productivity parameters include time spent on the high-risk activity. Furthermore, through the DEVS model and specific work process patterns, the

environmental conditions can also be considered that might affect the safety factor for certain types of activities, such as the operation of cranes.

- Safety factor

The DES tool was implemented at three demonstration sites of the ASHVIN project, #4, #5, and #6, and the WPP process models of these three implementations can be seen in section 4.2.1 in Figure 18, Figure 19, and Figure 20.

At demonstration site #4, the Productivity rate (workers), Utilisation rate (crane), Safety factor, and Total costs were the KPIs measured. Through the simulation of different input parameters, potential options could be calculated and compared. For each option, the DES was repeated for 1000 iterations to reach confidence and optimisation in the resulting outputs.

At demonstration site #5, the Productivity rate (trade), Resource efficiency rate (trade), Duration of concurrent trades, and Total costs were the KPIs measured. All finishing works can be included in the DES, enabling the planning of works where overlaps are minimised, and time and resources are used optimally across the construction site and trades. Certain trades require more time and resources than others, which will lead to complexity in planning the sequencing, here the division of the construction site into several workspaces can be an option. For demonstration site #5, the site was divided into three workspaces to enable multiple trades to conduct their work simultaneously for example. The DES tool could also visualise the different workspaces and their trades using the ASHVIN visualisation dashboard identified through colour codes.

At demonstration site #6, the Productivity rate (crane), Productivity rate (worker), Utilisation rate, Safety factor, and Total costs were the KPIs measured. The conducted work was at the site and also tracked in real-time through sensors that could send data to the ASHVIN platform through the ASHVIN API. Sensors were mounted to the cranes as well as to mounted concrete works to measure concrete quality. The demonstration site #6 simulated different input parameters of delivery intervals which led to different workflow efficiencies. Generally, the supply chain of the concrete works could be increased in efficiency.

4.3 CMT - A configuration management tool to track as-designed and as-built, as well as, to allow for seamless commissioning

The CMT tool, developed under T4.5 is a configuration management tool to effectively manage changes that occur during the construction phase of construction projects to ensure Quality Control (QC) and Quality Assurance (QA) (Khan, 2022). Construction projects involve various phases, from planning to final delivery, often influenced by incomplete information and assumptions made by professionals. Configuration management helps control these changes, ensuring consistency from As-planned to As-built. Through utilising DT scanning data and evaluating QC of constructed works at construction sites in real-time. The CMT integrates digital technologies to systematically manage and interrelate information across construction phases, providing a more accurate representation of the physical asset throughout its lifecycle with the help of real-time data (ibid). Ultimately, the CMT tool aims to provide insight

into As-designed/As-planned and As-built to maintain consistency among requirements, design, construction data, and asset information to enhance project QC and efficiency. The tool CMT is an extension of the 4DV-C tool to integrate visualisation comparison of As-planned and As-built within the ASHVIN platform (Łukaszewska, 2021).

The process also entails scanning the selected construction components using the available scanning equipment at the construction site, with a preference for Laser Scanners. The overarching aim of the CMT tool is to assess the conformity of built assets with the planned designs, employing 3D BIM models. This enables effective quality management of built assets, leveraging DT data for validation. The tool's utilisation frequency spans from the installation of specific construction elements to the final inspection post-construction. Its primary users include construction managers, who leverage it for daily operations, and a quality control team responsible for final assessments. Continuous utilisation of the CMT tool, augmented by real-time DT data capabilities, facilitates early detection of deviations in the construction process. This proactive approach allows for immediate evaluation of inconsistencies and calculation of their impacts, encompassing potential considerations of productivity, resource efficiency, and safety before the asset's commissioning.

The ASHVIN dashboard enhances this process by providing a visualisation of the As-built and As-planned models side by side, thereby facilitating a more intuitive and effective visual comparison between the two (Khan, 2022).

4.3.1 CMT Process Model

The CMT tool, as delineated in the process diagram of Figure 21, adheres to the BPMN standards. This diagram, created in the software Microsoft Visio, has been validated to ensure compliance with BPMN guidelines.

The process model is partitioned into three distinct lanes, each representing a specific area of operation for the tool: As-designed, As-built, and Deviation.

Figure 21: Process diagram of the CMT tool using the BPMN diagram method.

4.3.1.1 As-designed Lane

In the As-designed lane, the domain is on the design, the initial steps of the process describe how design data of components meant to be analysed is sent to the CM dashboard. As the CMT tool integrates with the 4DV-C tool, the initial steps taken by the CMT tool will follow the *DigitalAsset* classification.

4.3.1.2 As-built Lane

The process then moves to the As-built lane, here the process steps describe how the constructed components are scanned to be output into the *CM database*. The As-built lane encompasses the requisite actions that must be taken at the physical construction site. This is a pivotal step of the process for the effective functioning of the CMT tool is the integration of construction elements with the *CM database*. The following two functions taken within the CMT tool follow the *DataResources* and *BuiltEnvironment* classifications.

Applicable scanning procedures are implemented in this step of the process, which could either be through automatic or manual means. A proposed implementation of a scanning procedure would include *Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID)* and *Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) Beacons* applied to the building components as well as *Laser scanning*. *RFID* tags can provide configuration information of a component by transmitting real-time data. *BLE Beacons* can provide information regarding a component and if was conducted correctly. Further, *BLE Beacons* can be permanently mounted and provide asset tracking on a component over its life cycle, providing real-time information.

The scanning procedure can also include the process of configuring potential point clouds into 3D BIM models. In this deliverable, the actions taken in that step of the process are not delved into, however, technological solutions exist in the market today that can support this step of the process. Various Scan2BIM configurations exist in the market that can be utilised to this end, an example being the proposal of such a tool presented as a Use Case of buildingSMART as part of the BIM-SPEED EU Horizon2020 project (“Use Case: 3D Modeling of Existing Asset Based on Point Clouds (Scan2BIM) | Use Case Management,” 2022). Further, ASHVIN D4.5 delves deeper into the actions taken within the scanning procedure, providing insight into new scanning approaches such as terrestrial laser scanning (TSL) can provide a more optimal solution in the domain of QA/QC compared to more conventional solutions, as they can provide a more time efficient result during data collection (Tang et al., 2022). *Digital Forms* can be used to input informational data to the CM database of configuration data from the QA/QC team. For specific applications within a construction process, environmental sensor data of movement, temperature, noise etc can be of great importance when ensuring construction works are properly commissioned. Here mechanical sensors such as accelerometers and thermocouples can measure movement and temperature to ensure that construction works are installed properly when it comes to following the requirements. Further, data can also be manually collected and fed into the *CM database* in the form of *Digital Forms*.

4.3.1.3 As-designed Lane

The process then moves back to the As-designed lane where the collected data of the *CM database* is used to evaluate if the constructed asset conforms to a Production Quality Assessment and adheres to the initial design specifications. Here, a verification process is initiated, where consistency among requirements, and specified functions can be validated. A system such as the Swedish CoClass could be a viable option to classify and describe the functionality of the installed components, enabling a structured Asset Information Management (AIM) (CoClass, 2022). Utilising the CoClass system from the very beginning of the commissioning of constructed works enables continued management throughout the complete life-cycle of the constructed works by enabling a structured and information language that can be used even during the O&M phase. Another potential solution to offer further AIM of constructed works could be GTIN (Global Trade Item Number). GTIN can provide unique identification keys to products (currently a limited set of constructed components).

If the *Production Quality Assessment* proves to be satisfactory, where the As-built conforms to the initial design specifications the process is ended and the construction manager is informed of this, further information on verified works will be fed into the digital twin model.

4.3.1.4 Deviation Lane

The deviation lane of the CMT process is activated upon identifying discrepancies between the As-Designed and As-Built models, here the process of CMT continues as an evaluation of the impact of inconsistencies must be made and reported. This lane involves a thorough evaluation of the inconsistencies, an example being cost analysis of planned budget vs actual cost, where data from the construction planning phase is used here to identify and scrutinise potential cost variances. Inconsistencies for other parameters can be assessed here as well, depending on the data available from the *CM Database* on building elements as well as what can be gathered from the real-time data gathering of the as-built model for the DT. The output of the process where deviations are identified is the generation of an *Assessment Report*, which details the inconsistencies and their impacts.

The output of the CMT process in the form of *Asset Information Model (AIM)* and as-built BIM models can also be fed into the DT of the construction asset for use during the operation & maintenance phase. Further, the information of the QA/QC assessment report can also be exported as a PDF document for the project management team to analyse.

4.3.2 CMT Process Model Compliance

The process model for the CMT tool was constructed in Microsoft Visio and has been validated to ensure the process model follows the standardised ISO standard for the BPMN notation. The compliance framework for the CMT tool can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6: CMT Process Model Compliance Framework.

Compliance Areas	CMT Compliance
Documentation	The process is documented in a clear and detailed manner using the BPMN diagram method.
Standardisation	The process model was developed using only BPMN assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC 19510:2013.
Roles and Responsibilities	The specific roles involved in the process of CMT are not detailed in this process model, however, the process would likely involve stakeholders such as the Quality Control Team, Construction Managers, as well as construction firms and owners.
Compliance	The process model was developed using only BPMN assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC 19510:2013. Further, the process model has been verified and validated using the Microsoft Visio validation tool, to ensure the process model conforms to the BPMN standard methodology.
Ensuring process logic	For the CMT tool, process logic was taken into consideration when mapping out the process, following the logical steps taken within the tool. As the CMT tool can either output a positive result in the form of as-designed to as-built conformity, the process can stop if conformity is met. If conformity is not met, however, the deviation will be investigated and evaluated further.
Efficiency and Effectiveness	The process model was developed and designed for efficient and effective application, aiming to achieve the desired outcome with minimal wasted time, resources, or effort. The decoding process of the process reader should be a logical procedure (Winter et al., 2023).
Continuous Improvement	As the ASHVIN project aims to achieve TRL6 level of maturity, the process model of CMT is open for improvements and the original Microsoft Visio file can be provided for further development.

4.3.3 CMT Lean Lifecycle Integration

From a LC perspective, the CMT tool’s continuous quality control feature presents an opportunity to promptly identify and address impacts that might adversely affect the building’s lifecycle or other construction works. This tool is not only instrumental in mitigating immediate cost implications during the construction phase but also plays a crucial role in facilitating life-cycle calculations through the insights derived from the Assessment Report on inconsistencies and impact.

In terms of LC and its adaption and connection to the CMT tool, the tool does not inherently apply any lean concepts in its actual process. However, the outcome that can be derived from utilising the tool is where the lean concepts can come into play. Inherent of the LC process, waste is to be eliminated or at the very least minimised to its nth degree, instead focus should be put on value-creating actions taken. To this end, the CMT and its potential early detection of deviations can in that sense apply in a lean conceptual framework. Constructed works can be assessed on a real-time basis, where inconsistencies and variations that might affect other construction works or potentially the life cycle of an asset can be identified and evaluated from a life-cycle perspective. Further, the continuous use of the CMT tool throughout the construction process can ensure that any life-cycle evaluations and decisions of components can be scrutinised on a real-time basis to ensure that the built assets conform to the

planned life-cycle scope of components used through evaluations of component metadata and attributes. The CMT tool's continuous quality control feature presents an opportunity to promptly identify and address impacts that might adversely affect the building's lifecycle or other construction works. This tool is not only instrumental in mitigating immediate cost implications during the construction phase but also plays a crucial role in facilitating life-cycle calculations through the insights derived from the Assessment Report on inconsistencies and impact.

4.3.4 CMT Interoperability

The data requirements for the CMT tool to operate are the following:

- BIM model
 - A BIM model of the planned construction works is provided and enters the DT platform. The BIM model should follow the *DigitalAsset* classifications.
- As-built data
 - With the BIM model entered the DT platform, physical sensors and data collection methods are implemented at the construction site, to provide real-time as-built data and enable a DT model environment.
 - Asset information is gathered at the construction site through scanning and sensors using the *DataResources* classification.
 - The resulting As-built scan should follow the *BuiltEnvironment* classifications.
- Configuration Management database
 - The *CM database* is centralised, it is used in conjunction with the CMT tool to gather, store, and output data surrounding the BIM 3D model. Specific characteristics of the building components are also included in this process, where various function parameters and metadata are stored. Throughout the CMT process, the *CM database* is used to input and output data, which is used for the CMT tool, mainly however, the as-built data of the *CM database* of focus.

As for the CMT tool, the data focus is only the components and their attributes, including geometrical information as well as component-specific information. Thereby, additional information on the resources used to construct components in terms of temporary components used during the construction process, construction equipment, and construction workers are not analysed within the CMT process. The CMT process can therefore be seen as a somewhat simple process to run for a construction project. The API connectivity for CMT consists of the 3D model and its *geometrical* information, as well as component-specific information ensuring that informational data is transmitted to the *CM database*, as well as the 3D model and component informational input from scanning procedures. Data interoperability of the CMT tool and its process.

Regarding interoperability, the CMT tool is designed to support the ASHVIN platform, but its architecture, featuring an Application Programming Interface (API), enables broader integration capabilities with other DT applications. As highlighted in the ASHVIN project's D1.4 report, the tool incorporates Information Delivery Manuals (IDM) for the Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) processes.

The data exchange prerequisites are depicted in the process model of the CMT tool, using BPMN *data Object* and *Data Store* symbols respectively. The Data Object symbolises the ongoing or as-needed data collection via the DT platform i.e. input documents and input 3D models, while the *Data Store* of the CMT process model represents the *CM database* of installed products, facilitating the evaluation of As-built components.

The ontological context of the CMT tool is proposed in D1.2 by Khan, (2022) and can be seen in Figure 22.

Figure 22: CM process ontology (Khan, 2022).

4.3.5 CMT Process Model Decision-Making Points and Implementations

As for the CMT tool, demonstration sites #5 and #6 were chosen to showcase the process implementation.

The application of the CMT tool at demonstration site #5 of the ASHVIN project involved the early detection of deviations between as-designed and as-built certain areas of the Kineum high-rise building in Gothenburg, Sweden. During the construction, a 3D BIM model was created during the construction planning of the Kineum building focusing on the 16th floor of a building intended for hotel use. CMT tool implementation at demonstration site #5 was done specifically with a focus on windows doors, and curtain walls as well as general aesthetics. A BIM model was used as an As-designed input for the *ASHVIN DT Database* as well as the *CM Database*. As for the data gathering, the same areas as that of the acquired BIM model were then scanned using a Spot robot (Afsari, Kereshmeh, et al. 2021), equipped with a Leica BLK360 Laser scanner. The scanned as-built data comes in the form of a point cloud file, which was then transformed into a 3D BIM model. The scanned transformed 3D BIM model was

then input into the *CM Database*. The next step was to distinguish whether the scanned as-built model conformed to that of the as-designed model, here the client's performance requirements were taken into account, were the QC management team ensured that the constructed works from the as-built model lived up to the contracted requirements, as well as the stipulated AMA (Allmän material och byggbeskrivning), which is the Swedish QC praxis for construction works. In Figure 23, an example of an As-designed and As-built comparison can be found, here the As-designed would follow the *DigitalAsset* classifications and the As-built would follow the *BuiltEnvironment* classifications.

Figure 23: Configuration information for guest room door (As-designed and As-built).

At the Kineum construction site, various methods for identifying quality defects during the construction process were applied, including internal inspections, material inspections, and audits. This involves choosing appropriate checkpoints and standards for installations to meet industry and client requirements. For the CMT tool implementation of the Kineum site, focus was put on determining functional properties for doors and windows and curtain walls (e.g., *heat and sound insulation, fire resistance, safety*). This was done through conventional means with both tests and inspections, to ensure compliance with specified requirements. The requirements on the doors and windows were based on AMA specifications (Allmän material och byggbeskrivning), which is the Swedish QC praxis for construction works.

When looking to make comparisons between As-designed and As-built components such as windows, common reasons where there could end up being a difference between the two can be changes in window manufacturer or fire classification. The *CM dashboard* was used at the Kineum site to both do a visual aesthetic comparison as well as the specific parameters of the components on-site ensuring compliance with design specifications.

The CMT tool was also implemented at demonstration site #6 in Barcelona, where the concrete consolidation quality of concrete columns was assessed. In total, the building which consisted of 5 floors, included 60 individual column components which were all measured during the construction process to be visualised and analysed using the CMT tool. Of importance here was the data collection method, as the validity of the real-time data collected plays a part in the outcome and usefulness of the CMT tool

itself to gather valuable and actionable As-Built data. Based on data collection methods specified in the *DataResources* classifications enabling the creation of models that live up to the *BuiltEnvironment* classifications. A snapshot of the As-built aspect of the CMT tool can be seen in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Snapshot from CMT tool BPMN function: Collect data on building components of interest at the site (As-built).

For demonstration site #6, the use of sensors, accelerometers, and Ultra-Wideband (UWB) Radar were chosen as data collection methods, which could then be installed and mapped in the BIM model. In Figure 25, the CMT visualisation of concrete consolidation can be seen.

To ensure the strength and consolidation of the concrete, the choice of using a vibrating method that ensures an even distribution of vibrating energy across standard concrete columns is crucial. This involves deciding on the type and amount of vibration energy needed, based on factors such as mix type, form size, and amount of reinforcement. The adoption of IoT and convolutional neural network framework to monitor vibration quality in real-time was made at this stage. Choosing the data collection methodologies, sensors, and analytical frameworks to measure vibration depth and capture concrete surface images effectively is an important step in the process. Further ensuring these data collection methods are interoperable with the CMT tool and the ASHVIN platform is also involved in this procedure.

For vibration visualisation purposes, the use of Use of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) was made. The decision to employ UWB tracking systems for 3D tracking and visualisation of concrete vibration allows for precise localisation of the vibrator's tip, enhancing the ability to monitor and control the concrete consolidation process intelligently. Further, a positioning-sensor-based solution was adapted to provide real-time management of the concrete consolidation. This involved setting up algorithms to translate position-sensor data into actionable insights for managing workmanship quality effectively.

Another step was to install accelerometers directly on the vibrating machine or indirectly on the formwork to track the amount of time and energy devoted to vibrating concrete. This decision includes determining the placement of sensors for optimal data collection and the method for transmitting data to cloud services for analysis. MEMS

acceleration hardware sensors were adapted for the site to track factors such as sensitivity, temperature operating range, and measurement range are considered to ensure accurate data collection under varying conditions.

Figure 25: CMT tool visualisation: Concrete consolidation of demonstration site #6

The process of assessing concrete work quality based on accelerometer measurements and representing this quality on a 3D model using a colour spectrum involves decisions on the criteria for quality evaluation and the method of visualisation. This includes setting thresholds for what constitutes acceptable vibration and consolidation levels.

The final decision-making to use the configuration management tool on the ASHVIN platform for managing and visualising the data collected signifies a key point. This involves integrating IoT data with DT representations to provide a comprehensive overview of concrete quality and facilitate decision-making for construction managers.

As for the CMT KPI, the following KPIs can be derived from the utilisation of the CMT tool.

4.3.5.1 CMT Productivity KPI

- Positioning of building elements (laser scanner, RFIDs)
- As-built model verification for progress control and deviation check (point cloud scans, 360° cameras)

4.3.5.2 CMT Resource Efficiency KPI

- Wastage from concrete casting (mechanical sensors)

4.3.5.3 CMT Cost KPI

- As-planned vs As-built Information (Digital Forms, RFIDs)
- Rework costs (laser scanner)
- Asset information management for LCA (CM Database, logbook)

4.3.5.4 CMT Safety KPI

- Strength of structural components (mechanical sensors)
- Deviation from design (cameras)

4.4 SMT - Privacy ensuring safety management, simulation, and training tool

The SMT tool serves as an enhancement to the 4DV-C tool, focusing on bolstering construction site safety. It leverages the existing GIS platform to provide safety managers with insights into potential hazards on the site and analyse historical construction activities without compromising individual workers' privacy. Given the construction industry's high risk and frequent accidents, enhancing site safety protocols can significantly reduce incidents. This initiative is crucial for ensuring worker safety and health, sustaining project productivity, and minimising compensation for job-related injuries. The tool will augment the 4DV-C by tracking construction workers, equipment, machinery, and other objects on-site using the DTT game engine platform for privacy protection. This tracking utilises BLE beacons, upgrading the current DTT platform for personnel tracking on a GIS map to incorporate the DTT game engine with 4DV-C.

Additionally, the SMT tool incorporates a sub-process for Targeted Training Programs as developed in T6.3, designed specifically to cater to the unique safety requirements of each construction site, as well as the follow-up of the implemented targeted safety programs (Claeson-Jonsson et al. 2024).

4.4.1 SMT Process Model

The SMT tool, as delineated in the process diagram of Figure 26, adheres to the BPMN standards. This diagram, created in the software Microsoft Visio, has been validated to ensure compliance with BPMN guidelines.

The process model is partitioned into two lanes, representing the SMT tool implementation including the sub-process of Targeted Training Programs and follow-up and evaluation. Furthermore, if a safety alert is detected, the second lane is activated, in a similar fashion to that of the deviation lane of the CMT tool process model. Here, the ASHVIN safety dashboard is opened to evaluate the safety infraction detected as well as the evaluation of the implemented targeted training programs. The outcome of such a case will be an assessment report on safety infractions and impact. Derived from the process model are also the two groupings within the process models of *DigitalAsset* and *DataResources* classifications.

Figure 26: Process diagram of the SMT tool using the BPMN diagram method.

4.4.2 SMT Process Model Compliance

The process model for the SMT tool was constructed in Microsoft Visio and has been validated to ensure the process model follows the standardised ISO standard for the BPMN notation. The compliance framework for the SMT tool can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: SMT Process Model Compliance Framework.

Compliance Areas	SMT Compliance
Documentation	The process model for the SMT tool is documented in a clear and detailed manner using the BPMN diagram method.
Standardisation	The process model was developed using only BPMN assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC 19510:2013.
Roles and Responsibilities	The specific roles involved in the process of SMT are not detailed in this process model, however, the process would likely involve stakeholders such as the Safety Management Team.
Compliance	The process model was developed using only BPMN assets, conforming to the ISO standard of ISO/IEC 19510:2013. Further, the process model has been verified and validated using the Microsoft Visio validation tool, to ensure the process model conforms to the BPMN standard methodology.
Ensuring process logic	For the SMT tool, process logic was taken into consideration when mapping out the process, following the logical steps taken within the tool. As the SMT tool can output a positive result in the form of no safety infractions detected, the process can stop if no infractions are found. If safety infractions are detected, however, the safety infractions will be investigated and evaluated further.
Efficiency and Effectiveness	The process model was developed and designed for efficient and effective application, aiming to achieve the desired outcome with minimal wasted time, resources, or effort. The decoding process of the process reader should be a logical procedure (Winter et al., 2023).
Continuous Improvement	As the ASHVIN project aims to achieve TRL6 level of maturity, the process model of SMT is open for improvements and the original Microsoft Visio file can be provided for further development.

4.4.3 SMT Lean Lifecycle Integration

From a LC perspective, the SMT serves most of its purpose solely concerning the safety aspects of the construction site. However, as the SMT tool integrates with the 4DV-C tool, the LC aspect of the 4DV-C tool in its planning assessment, ensuring that construction site safety is covered will minimise stoppages in work due to safety infractions or accidents.

4.4.4 SMT Interoperability

Regarding interoperability, the SMT tool interacts with the *ASHVIN DT Database* through the *DigitalAsset* and *DataResources* classifications. Furthermore, the SMT acts as an extension to the 4DV-C tool and can be integrated using the ConDT ontology, connecting through the IDEF0 *Controls* and *Mechanisms* of the ConDT framework.

4.4.5 SMT Process Model Decision-Making Points and Implementations

Regarding the SMT tool, the pivotal aspect of decision-making within the process model pertains to the assessment of potential safety violations through the ASHVIN Dashboard. Within this dashboard, potential safety violations identified at construction sites are displayed and subjected to evaluation. The SMT tool serves as an extension of the 4DV-C tool, and its operation alongside the 4DV-C extension allows for the integration of more focused and detailed safety considerations.

Furthermore, depending on the specific implementation and focus of the targeted training program component of the SMT tool, different areas of the safety aspect at construction sites can be evaluated. An example of a targeted training program was proposed in D6.3 *“A SMART goal could be to reduce the number of fall-related incidents on the construction site by 25% within six months through the implementation of a comprehensive fall prevention training program. Setting realistic and achievable goals ensures that the training program is designed to address the identified safety needs and objectives of the construction site”*. (Claeson-Jonsson et al. 2024).

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The work conducted in this deliverable of the conceptualised process models is specifically targeted to delineate the use of the tools specific to the ASHVIN project for the construction phase DT domain.

It can be stated that through running the tools (4DV-C, DES, CMT and SMT) of this deliverable, positive outcomes can be delineated. Through the decision-making routines inherent to the tools, the ASHVIN platform is in the form of KPI and visualisation dashboards. Presenting KPIs and visualisation dashboards. These tools facilitate project managers and project teams in selecting the most effective and resource-efficient construction strategies. This is achieved by conducting simulations and assessing various scenarios with distinct input parameters of the 4DV-C and DES tools. As for the interoperability across the ASHVIN construction, this is enabled through the ConDT ontology and the OpenAPI ASHVIN API. Using the 4DV-C tool and process model as a basis, the natural integration of DES will enable the 4DV-C tool to improve its sequencing. The CMT tool can be used to ensure that the *BuiltEnvironment* is up to the standards set by the project requirements of the *DigitalAsset* DT. Furthermore, the CMT tool will be used to continually evaluate the construction process. The SMT tool integrated into the 4DV-C tool can enhance the construction site safety parameters unique to the site itself focusing on specific risk assessments and targeted training programs. The interoperability of data collection at the construction site is governed by the *DataResources* classifications, to enable real-time data integration for the four tools, and to ensure that the ontology of the data sources and their API connectivity follows the set requirements of the ASHVIN parameters.

Decision-making within the construction industry needs the adoption of more data-driven approaches. Through the adoption of DT methodologies, such as the DT platform and its ASHVIN toolkit, this will become even more viable and powerful than what is available in the market today. Decisions made within the ASHVIN toolkit will be based on objective data parameters, leading to more accurate and valid decision-making.

The process models mapped out in this deliverable were developed on early ASHVIN Platform versions, meaning, further development might enable the tools to extend their applicability in certain regards. Furthermore, the demonstration and application of the tools of ASHVIN have also been limited in nature, as the ASHVIN project is a research and innovation project with the maturity level of TRL6.

The process models are largely theoretical in their current state, and further application and implementation would be needed to refine their operation. As the process models comply with both the ISO standards of BPMN and IDEF0 depending on the process, improvements and further refinements could easily be made to the process models.

Concerning the interoperability of the tools and their data utilisation in a DT context, development has been made with the ASHVIN platform as a focal point, incorporating the ontology of ConDT and OAS connectivity. Nevertheless, the primary objective of the ASHVIN project has consistently been the development of open-source solutions. In alignment with this goal, the adaptation of ASHVIN tools may exhibit applicability across alternative DT platforms.

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